

A Review of the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem of The Gambia

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Abstract

Over the years, entrepreneurship programmes have gained momentum and expanded in The Gambia focusing on the national development priorities (MoFEA, 2018). The introduction of these programmes that are supporting youth and women entrepreneurship development has been seen in many sectors of the economy. However, a review of the entrepreneurship ecosystem shows an un-coordinated and limited synergy amongst the different actors of the ecosystem as well as the programmes being implemented (MoHERST & OACPS, 2022). This has resulted to a low entrepreneurial output of the programmes within the economy

Conscious of this situation, this paper seeks to review the current entrepreneurship ecosystem in The Gambia with a view to propose viable options of ensuring closer linkages between the actors and the programmes being delivered. It reviews the policy drive, actors of the ecosystem, current programmes, support structures in place, coordination mechanisms, and the types of available funding for entrepreneurship in The Gambia (Sowe, S., 2024).

The paper concluded by identifying the gaps within the entrepreneurship ecosystem and proposed recommendations aimed at ensuring an effective and efficient entrepreneurship ecosystem in The Gambia (MoHERST & OACPS, 2022).

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship Ecosystem, Review, Financing, Business Development, The Gambia.*

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Introduction

Entrepreneurship education has been widely adopted as a global phenomenon to help provide business skills and the development of entrepreneurial mindsets amongst actors (Johannes Lindner, 2020). It has been relied on to support the establishment of entrepreneurship ecosystems. Thus, (Isenberg, 2010) described it as a complex adaptive system made up of many individual parts or agents. These parts and agents are expected to follow specific set rules, which will allow them to work in a coordinated manner, based on the locality and other conditions linked to their ecosystem. Thus, Isenberg's definition provides requisites for the establishment of entrepreneurship ecosystems for the priority sectors of the economy factoring regional, gender and social inclusion.

Most developing countries are depending on well-established entrepreneurship ecosystems to help address un-employment (Shu et al., 2020). The projects and programmes from such ecosystem are

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being used to help curb irregular migration amongst youth. These programmes can be in priority sectors of the economy including education, health, agriculture, tourism, and digital economy in line with the development needs of the country.

Towards fully utilizing the potential of the entrepreneurship ecosystem, it is prudent that an assessment is done to establish the current trend, identify gaps, and propose viable options for a well-established entrepreneurship ecosystem for The Gambia. Hence, the necessity of this paper, for use by policy and academic research towards advancing entrepreneurship education and development in The Gambia.

Entrepreneurship Policy Drive in The Gambia

In responding to the set targets of the Green Recovery Focus National Development Plan (2023 – 2027), different sectors are implementing various policies and programmes relative to entrepreneurship education and development. The National Entrepreneurship Policy focuses on how to provide strategic direction and establishing programmes for entrepreneurship development (MoTIE, 2022). Similarly, the Gambia National MSME Policy emphasises on putting measures towards accessing appropriate finance, technology, capital, market and mentorship for all MSMEs and providing a legal and regulatory environment that is business friendly (GIPEA, 2019).

Related to these is the National Youth Policy (2019 – 2028), focuses on empowering the youth of The Gambia for employability and enterprise development towards optimal contribution to national growth and development (MOYS, 2019). It has made specific pronouncements for the establishment of an entrepreneurship Fund, which seen the creation of the National Entrepreneurship Development Initiative (NEDI, 2024). Since establishment, NEDI continue to provide entrepreneurship funds to youth across all regions of The Gambia. Also, with the Women Entrepreneurship Fund has been the disbursement of funds to youth and women respectively (MoGCSW, 2020).

However, the implementation of these funds has been criticized for their lack of entrepreneurial training and skills sets as well as weak monitoring mechanisms. This situation can be linked to the un-coordinated nature of the ecosystem, which could have provided the necessary resources and partnerships to ensure desired entrepreneurship projects in The Gambia.

At the level of education and training, the Education Sector Policy and Strategy (ESSP, 2016 – 2030) promotes the introduction of entrepreneurship education as early as Grade 4 and this is aligned with the MoHERST Strategic Plan (2021 – 2025) and the National TVET Policy (2021 – 2030) which also emphasizes the introduction of entrepreneurship courses in all programmes offered at tertiary and higher education institutions (MoHERST, 2023). In achieving this policy drive, the National Accreditation and Quality Assurance Authority (NAQAA) is leading the inclusion of innovation and entrepreneurship training in all courses of tertiary and higher education institutions. This is being supported by coordinated internships and industrial placements as part of the curriculum to support the alignment with labour market needs as seen in the USET embedded entrepreneurship delivery approach (Sowe & Mwila, 2023).

To achieve an effective entrepreneurship ecosystem, it is recommended that national STI policies are developed in consistent with the ECOWAS STI Policy (ECOPOST) and the African Union Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Policy (Andreas Blom, 2016). This will ensure STI serves as an enabler to regional integration and business development. These instruments will serve as framework support for international collaboration in the area of research and innovation development with development partners.

Actors and Elements of the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem in The Gambia

In The Gambia, the actors within the entrepreneurship ecosystem are found in different institutions, manifesting and un-coordinated and limited expertise on how to run and implement the respective elements within entrepreneurship programmes (ITC, 2020). The entrepreneurship ecosystem mainly has four broad components, which includes institutional arrangements, public resources, financing, market demand and business activities (Stam, 2015). Stam further argued that these components need to be considered towards serving as catalyst for entrepreneurship development. This suggests that the life cycle of each of these components must be identified and understood to ensure the ecosystem is fully functional and responsive to the needs of the respective actors.

Also, (Isenberg, 2010) argued that the entrepreneurship ecosystem consists of set of individual elements such as leadership, culture, capital markets, and open-minded customers that combine in a complex way. These elements in isolation are supportive to entrepreneurship growth, but they are insufficient to be sustained without working together. Hence the need to ensure the actors involving individuals from academia, industry, research, and the community consider these as part of their processes.

Additionally, (Malecki, 2018) discussed that universities play a critical role in establishing entrepreneurship ecosystems and defined entrepreneurial ecosystem as consisting of a complexity of actors, roles, and environmental factors that interact to determine the entrepreneurial performance of a given region or locality. Skills sets on communication and coordination are needed to help bring all the relevant actors and elements of the ecosystem. This will help facilitate the establishment and adaptation of transversal skills such as communication, teamwork, critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and leadership (Ribeiro et al., 2016).

Towards establishing entrepreneurship ecosystems, (S Oluotase, P Brijlal, B Yan, E Ologundudu, 2018) discussed that the entrepreneurial ecosystem elements are crucial towards translating entrepreneurial intentions, and thus It is incumbent especially on government to create and sustain an ecosystem that not only support but stimulate entrepreneurship

The above-mentioned parameter will help establish a vibrant entrepreneurship ecosystem ensuring there is leadership and coordination in all entrepreneurship programmes and projects in The Gambia.

Institutional Programmes

In The Gambia, there is a policy drive to include entrepreneurship training in all tertiary and higher education institutions (NAQAA, 2023). This approach is aligned to the USET embedded entrepreneurship in core engineering curricula, which is also lined up for adoption at the TVET level. In the content delivery drive, (Manneh et al., 2020) argued that the entrepreneurial intention plays a significant role towards building student's entrepreneurial attitudes and desire to establishing businesses. For this, they argued that the entrepreneurship courses offered at the University of The Gambia (UTG) have been designed to expose students to the application of business. These courses includes entrepreneurship and small business management modules that has inspired students to develop entrepreneurial orientations.

For many years, the private sector through the respective chambers of commerce for youth and women have implemented many entrepreneurship programmes in The Gambia. For example, through external donor funding mainly sources from the European Union Migration Trust Fund, programmes such as the Youth Empowerment Project (YEP Gambia) focused on skills

development and entrepreneurship for youth and the She Trades Gambia have supported women entrepreneurs by providing training and networking opportunities (ITC, 2020).

Most of these entrepreneurship programmes have been seen in many sectors, but due to their lack of relevant skills as part of the delivery and coupled with un-coordinated monitoring, most of these beneficiaries failed to establish and maintain the start-ups they supported. This is because these entrepreneurship programmes lack linkages with academic competencies and business development support that could have been provided by the entrepreneurship hubs established in academic institutions.

Despite the presence of weak linkages with academic institutions, youth entrepreneurs are aware of digital opportunities and the majority perceive the benefits of e-commerce and thus the spur of fintech across the country, despite the challenges on security and high cost for its implementation e-commerce technologies. The surge in fintechs will require the support, supervision and regulation by both the Public Utility and Regulatory Authority (PURA) as well as the Central Bank of The Gambia (CBG). This will ensure there are coordinated standards, customer satisfaction, as well as effective service delivery.

Entrepreneurship development in the agriculture sector has been sparsely observed, and (Kemo Mamanding Fatty et al., 2023) discussed that within the agriculture sector in The Gambia, there is a need to provide business development support to employees towards identifying businesses that can propel and generate income. To achieve this, the agriculture sector needs to align their entrepreneurial support programmes with tertiary institutions to ensure they facilitate and support in instilling entrepreneurial attributes and provide adequate resources and monitoring processes.

Support Structure for Entrepreneurship Development

The innovation and entrepreneurship curriculum in The Gambia is delivered to help instil entrepreneurial orientation and mindsets amongst student trainees (Sowe, 2023). As part of this delivery approach, there is established an entrepreneurship hub that provides niche support to entrepreneurship development through business, internship, prototyping, and commercialization. The delivery approach is being replicated in all the regional TVET centres being rolled out by the government as part of the tertiary and higher education transformation agenda.

It has been argued that entrepreneurship hubs are facilitators of creativity, and they support interactive collaboration to ensure entrepreneurial output (Dr & Friederici, 2017). Therefore, their performance will depend on the local context and the active involvement of all actors and elements in the entrepreneurship ecosystem to see that these hubs are vibrant and responsive.

Also, the hubs being used by NEDI and the mixed farming centres under the Ministry of Agriculture can be revitalized to serve as entrepreneurship hubs and as well be linked to the regional TVET centres across the country. This will widen entrepreneurship support across all regions in The Gambia.

In addition to other short-cycle support, the Government has introduced a Skills, Innovation and Entrepreneurship (SIE) Fund, that will support widening access to technical skills and entrepreneurship programmes through start-ups including mentorship. This support will be succeeded by the National Research and Innovation Fund that is being created through a legislative process (DSTI, 2024).

Coordination of Entrepreneurship Programmes

Despite entrepreneurship being cross cutting, involving academic, business, and commercialization processes. It has been observed that, there has been no Ministry or institution that is leading and coordinating all entrepreneurship activities in The Gambia. This is expected to include engaging with Chambers of Commerce and industries.

At the level of Government there are two funds that are already in place to support entrepreneurship development and another one currently being legislated to support wider academic and industrial entrepreneurship development. The National Entrepreneurship Development Initiative (NEDI) and the Women Entrepreneurship Fund, targeting youth and women entrepreneurship support.

The establishment of a National Research and Innovation Fund is aimed at encouraging funding for research, innovation and entrepreneurship activities across priority sectors of the economy for an increased generation of new knowledge, technologies, and innovations that contribute to the country's socio-economic growth and development.

Lessons from Senegal, in which the sources of funds, strong leadership, closer collaboration with academic institutions, and effective communication would be relied on to help raise awareness on entrepreneurship potential for development (Seck et al., 2015). This approach helps to widen open-mindedness of actors as they engage in business related activities within an ecosystem.

Gaps in the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

There is non-established ecosystem that has resulted to un-coordinated funding leading to premature entrepreneurship and start-up programmes, the lack of an academic programme and support structures to facilitate start-up development. Under this situation, there is a lot of duplication of efforts and weak linkages that has not resulted to the desired outcome for entrepreneurship programmes and projects. In addition, it has been observed that the selection process and monitoring for entrepreneurship beneficiaries is weak, this is because of weak leadership and no guidelines to support the full cycle of entrepreneurship programmes.

Also, since there is no dedicated fund for entrepreneurship for use by all actors of the ecosystem, this has reduced the chances of support to wider beneficiaries. The ecosystem is left with donor funded entrepreneurship projects and the youth and women entrepreneurship funds, which provide lesser numbers of beneficiary support.

Also, challenges of putting in place monitoring mechanisms for entrepreneurship projects and building skills for entrepreneurial orientation amongst actors has been observed. Putting in place these aspects is very critical towards establishing a responsive ecosystem.

Discussion and Recommendations

To put in place a well-established entrepreneurship ecosystem, there is a need to identify the actors and factors of the ecosystem, as discussed by (Isenberg, 2010). This will help bring all the needed elements and activities of a given ecosystem, ensuring collaborative approach.

Towards widening and enhancing entrepreneurship in The Gambia, it is recommended to utilize support structures such as mixed farming centres, community-based production centres, as well as the entrepreneurship and innovation hubs. These will be used for the purposes of building capacities as well as facilitate business productivity amongst entrepreneurs.

To enhance coordination, there is a need to put in place governance structures and standard operating procedures in detailed manuals for all entrepreneurship funded programmes in The Gambia. This will be in consistent with the National Research and Innovation Fund Bill, which has proposed governance and administrative structures for the management and coordination and implementation of the fund. This ensures that entrepreneurship programmes and projects are effectively and efficiently managed to improve the country's international competitiveness. The structures should put in place clear cut governance and implementing procedures to support entrepreneurship development in The Gambia.

Practically, the weak coordination should be addressed by an institution that should be identified to lead and ensure there is established a committee to monitor all entrepreneurship programmes in The Gambia.

The need for a policy on internships and industrial placement to serve as an enabler to entrepreneurship programmes in The Gambia. This will create an alignment between the institutional academic programmes and industry need requirements of specific sectors.

Also, there is a need for regular popularization platforms such as entrepreneurship and innovation fairs where all the actors will meet to share their products and processes as well as exchange business ideas towards a common understanding and closer collaboration.

Conclusion

Realising the full potential of the entrepreneurship ecosystem in The Gambia remains a challenge. However, the ecosystem serves as a hope to address the current un-employment seen in all sectors of the economy (GBOS, 2023). The establishment of a functional ecosystem will create a pathway for the effective delivery of entrepreneurship programmes and projects in The Gambia. This will put in place a coordinated approach bringing all the actors and necessary factors needed to push forward entrepreneurship development in The Gambia.

It is expected that regular reviews on the functionality of the governance and monitoring systems needs to be conducted to assess the relevance and effectiveness of respective entrepreneurship programmes as well as the viability of the wider ecosystem. For example, proper coordination would be needed in the implementation of the National Research and Innovation Fund upon establishment, this will support the coordination and streamlining of all entrepreneurship projects in all priority sectors of the economy factoring regional, gender and social inclusion.

Specifically, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for entrepreneurship programmes is important, as it forms basis for ensuring entrepreneurship success and outcomes. This will ensure beneficiaries are mentored and provided with entrepreneurial and business skills all along their entrepreneurship cycle.

Since entrepreneurship is cross-cutting in many sectors, it is best to have an institution that leads the coordination of all entrepreneurship projects and programmes in The Gambia, and to this it is recommended that the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, Science and Technology leads the entrepreneurship drive in The Gambia based on its critical role and cross-cutting function in the human capital development, science, technology and innovation role within the economy.

Finally, it is critical for The Gambia to engage with the ecosystems in Senegal and other countries within the sub-region for knowledge transfer and joint-entrepreneurship projects towards building and enhancing local capacities for business development.

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